

5000 METR MASOFAGA YUGURUVCHILARNI MAXSUS
JISMONIY TAYYORGARLIGINI TUZILISHI

O'ktamov Dilyorbek Tojiboyevich

Andijon davlat universiteti sport va san'at
fakulteti fakultetlararo jismoniy tarbiya va
sport kafedrası v.b.dotsent.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada 5000 metr masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni yillik tayyorgarlik mashg'ulotlarida musobaqalarga tayyorlash oldidan olingan tadqiqot natijalari va maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligining tuzilishi berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Maxsus tayyorgarlik, sportchilar, 5000 metr masofaga yugurish, natijalar dinamikasi, yuklamalar hajmi.

Аннотация: В статье представлены результаты исследования и структура специальной физической подготовки бегунов на 5000 метров перед подготовкой их к соревнованиям на ежегодных тренировочных занятиях.

Ключевые слова: Специальная подготовка, спортсмены, бег на 5000 метров, динамика результатов, объем нагрузок.

Abstract: This article presents the results of a study conducted during the annual training sessions of 5000-meter runners before preparing for competitions and the structure of special physical training.

Keywords: Special training, athletes, 5000-meter run, dynamics of results, volume of loads.

Xozirgi kunda dunyoda Yengil atletikaning 5000 metr masofaga yugurish ommalashgan sport turlaridan bo'lsada, ammo sport natijalarini kun sayin o'sib borishi sportchilar tayyorlash tizimida nafaqat iqtidorli sportchilarni izlab topish qolaversa, mashg'ulot jarayonlarini samarali boshqarish va rejalashtirish bilan ham ahamiyatlidir. Shuning uchun ham sportchilar tayyorlash tizimini yangi rejalari va dasturlarini ishlab chiqish va amaliyot jarayoniga tatbiq etishni taqozo etadi. Jaxon

sport amaliyotida hozirgi vaqtda 5000 metr masofaga yugurish turida Afrika qit'asi vakillari peshqadamlik qilayotgan bo'lsada, ammo dunyoning boshqa davlat sportchilari ham chempionlik unvoniga erishish uchun harakat qilmoqdalar. Sportchilar tayyorlash tizimida rejalashtirish va mashg'ulotlarni boshqarish masalalariga ilmiy asosda yondashmoqdalar. Ammo buning o'zi yuqori malakali sportchilarni tayyorlash uchun yetarli emas. Shuning uchun har bir sportchini nafaqat mashg'ulot jarayonidagi faoliyati qolaversa, musobaqalarga tayyorlash jarayonlarini ham to'g'ri tashkil qilish, yuklamalar nisbatini to'g'ri taqsimlash rejalashtirishni optimal variantlarini ishlab chiqish kerakligini ko'rsatmoqda.

Yurtimizda 5000 metr masofaga yugurish bo'yicha ma'lumotlarni o'rganish va tahlil natijalari jahon arenalarida ko'rsatilgan hamda ko'rsatilayotgan sport natijalaridan sezilarli darajada 2 daqiqa va undan ortiq vaqtga ortda qolayotganligimizni ko'rsatmoqda. Bu esa 5000 metr masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni tayyorlash tizimini tubdan isloh qilish va boshqarishning yangi innovatsion texnologiyalarini amaliyotga joriy qilish barobarida sohadagi dolizarb vazifalardan ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi: 5000 metr masofaga yuguruvchilarni maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligiga musobaqalarga tayyorlash.

Tadqiqot vazifalari: 5000 metr masofaga yuguruvchilarni tadqiqot oldidan maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligini aniqlash, mashg'ulot yuklamalarini taqsimlanishi bo'yicha istiqbolli rejalar va boshqaruv tizimini o'rganish

5000 metr masofaga yuguruvchilarni yillik mashg'ulotlar dasturini ishlab chiqish va pedagogik tajribada ilmiy asoslash.

Tadqiqotda qo'llanilgan usullar va kutilayotgan natijalar

Biz tadqiqot jarayonida O'zbekistonning uzoq masofalarga yuguruvchi sportchilarini sport natijalarini o'rganish va tahlil etish barobarida ularni maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini aniqlash bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqot olib bordik. Maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik natijalarini qiyosiy tahlili quyidagi 1-2 jadvallarda berildi.

**Tajriba guruxi sinaluvchilarni tadqiqot boshida jismoniy tayyorgarligini
shakllanish dinamikasi**

1-jadval

	F,I,Sh	10 0m yuguri sh (soniya)	10 00m yuguri sh (daq- soniya)	30 00m yuguri sh (daq- soniya)	50 00m yuguri sh (daq- soniya)	TU S (sm)	J TUX S (sm)	J TO' XS (sm)	O OS 100m masofa ga (marta)
N	Mutalipov	1 2,51	0 2:47,5	0 8:55,0	1 5:19,0	34	6 40	2 138	5 1
A	Turg'unov	1 2,21	0 2:50,0	0 9:07,0	1 6:05,0	26	6 26	2 109	4 9
	Mamatko milov O	1 2,72	0 2:49,5	0 9:21,2	1 6:11,0	16	6 24	2 080	5 4
	Tojixujay ev X	1 2,35	0 2:54,9	0 9:28,5	1 5:50,5	22	6 18	2 115	5 2
	Mamatqul ov Z	1 2,05	0 2:54,2	0 9:05,1	1 5:23,5	29	6 28	2 125	5 1
	Xudayber diyev J	1 2,81	0 2:58,4	0 9:18,0	1 5:56,1	27	6 30	2 138	5 1
	Xakimov Yaxyo	1 3,06	0 2:52,5	0 9:19,5	1 6:02,3	26	6 22	2 062	5 2
	Boltaboje v O	1 3,11	0 2:53,0	0 9:24,0	1 6:13,8	18	6 17	2 039	5 4
	Inomov S	1 3,1	0 2:56,2	0 9:31,6	1 6:12,0	22	6 01	2 035	5 2
	Xakimov	1	0	0	1		5	2	5

0	A	3,21	2:51,3	9:33,0	6:15,3	21	96	037	4
1	Zaynobov	1	0	0	1		6	2	5
	X	3,32	2:52,2	9:06,0	5:28,0	26	21	142	2
2	Odilov B	1	2	9:	15		6	2	5
		3,51	:56,6	26,9	:54,3	21	01	081	3
	O'rtacha	1	2	9:	1		6	2	5
	ko'rsatkich	2,83	:52,7	16,3	5:51,8	25	20	097	2
σ – СИГМА									

**Nazorat guruxi sinaluvchilarni tadqiqot boshida jismoniy tayyorgarligini
shakllanish dinamikasi**

2-jadval

	F,I,Sh	10 0m yuguri sh (soniya)	10 00m yuguri sh (daq- soniya)	30 00m yuguri sh (daq- soniya)	50 00m yuguri sh (daq- soniya)	TU S (sm)	J TUX S (sm)	J TO' XS (sm)	O OS 100m masofa ga (marta)
	Asqarov J	1 2,65	0 2:49,5	0 8:59,0	1 5:22,2		6 35	2 130	5 0
	Aldashev	1 2,31	0 2:53,0	0 9:11,5	1 6:10,2		6 18	2 105	4 8
	Saidjonov	1 2,83	0 2:51,5	0 9:24,2	1 6:15,0		6 20	2 054	5 3
	Ikromov	1 2,42	0 2:55,9	0 9:33,1	1 5:53,5		6 15	2 104	5 1
	Xasanov	1 2,20	0 2:55,5	0 9:10,1	1 5:26,5		6 23	2 120	5 0

	Xolbo'tay	1	0	0	1		6	2	5
	ev A	2,93	2:59,4	9:23,0	5:59,1	25	22	131	1
	Shokirov	1	0	0	1		6	2	5
	B	3,22	2:54,5	9:24,5	6:06,3	21	15	045	1
	Soliyev	1	0	0	1		6	2	5
	Sh	3,22	2:56,0	9:27,9	6:15,8	15	15	025	2
	Mingboye	1	0	0	1		5	2	5
	v I	3,19	2:58,2	9:34,6	6:15,1	18	92	024	1
	Kamolov	1	0	0	1		5	2	5
0	E	3,28	2:54,2	9:34,4	6:18,1	18	91	030	3
	Dadabola	1	0	0	1		6	2	5
1	yev X	3,41	2:55,1	9:09,4	5:31,3	21	15	131	0
	Kimsanov	1	0	0	1		5	2	5
2	J	3,62	2:59,6	9:28,7	5:57,3	19	95	049	2
	O'rtacha	1	0	0	1		6	2	5
	ko'rsatkich	2,94	2:55,2	9:21,7	5:57,5	20	13	079	1
	σ – сирма								

Izox: JTUS- Joydan turib uzunlikka sakrash, JTUXS- Joydan turib uch xatlab sakrash, JTO'XS- Joydan turib o'n xatlab sakrash, OOS- oyoqdan oyoqqa sakrash, TTU- to'ldirma to'pni uloqtirish.

L.P.Sergeyenko tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligi model ko'rsatkich jadvalida quyidagi nazorat mashqlari 15-17, 16-17, 18-20 yoshlar ko'rsatkichida berilgan (3-jadval).

**Uzoq masofalarga yuguruvchilarni model ko'rsatkichlari
(L.P.Sergeyenko) bo'yicha.**

3-jadval

Nazorat mashqlari	Yosh ko'rsatkichlari		
	15-17	16-17	18

						-20
		Sport razryadi				
		II		I		S UN
100m yugurish (s)	12,8	12,2	12,2	1,7	11,5	
1000m yugurish (daq.s)	2,48,9	2,40,8	2,38,2	2,32,2	2,30,0	
3000m yugurish (daq.s)	9,09,4	8,43,5	8,39,9	8,20,0	8,13,9	
5000m yugurish (daq.s)	16,00,0	15,15,0	15,00,0	1,4,26,0	14,15,0	
JTUS	24,9	26,2	26,3	2,74	27,7	
JTUXS	75,5	79,3	79,5	8,27	83,7	
JTO'XS	25,48	26,75	27,19	2,827	28,61	

Biz tomonimizdan o'tkazilgan tadqiqotda 5000 metr masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligi L.P.Sergeyenko tomonidan berilgan ma'lumotlarga nisbatan maxsus chidamlilikda ya'ni 1000, 3000, 5000 metr masofalarga yugurish. Oyoqni portlovchi kuchini aniqlashda joyidan turib uzunlikka sakrash, joyidan uch xatlab sakrash, joyidan turib o'n xatlab sakrash sinovida va 100 metr masofaga maxsus tezkor kuch sifatleri bo'yicha ortda qolayotganligimiz kuzatildi.

5000 metr masofaga yuguruvchilarni jismoniy tayyorgarligini o'rganishi bo'yicha o'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalari quyidagi xulosalarni qayd etish imkonini berdi.

1. 5000 metr masofaga yugurish bo'yicha sportchilarni tayyorlash dasturlari bugungi kunda eskirganligi va samaradorligi ko'zlangan natijalarni bermayotganligini ko'rsatdi.

2. 5000 metr masofaga yuguruvchilarni maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligini aniqlash bo'yicha o'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra maxsus chidamlilik bo'yicha boshqa olimlar tomonidan bergan model ko'rsatkichlardan sezilarli darajada ortda qolayotganligimizni ko'rsatdi.

3. O'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijasiga ko'ra 5000 metr masofaga yugurish bo'yicha sportchilarni tayyorgarlik dasturlari va rejalarini yangi innovatsion texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish va boshqarish tizimini ishlab chiqish zarurligini taqozo etadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati.

1. Olimov Mukhsinbek Sotivoldiyevich, DYNAMIK DER AUSBILDUNG DES SPEZIALKÖRPERLICHEN TRAININGS IM LANGSTRECKENLÄUFER. Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. Vol.1 Issue 1.5 Pedagogical sciences. 68-76 p. <http://berlinstudies.de/index.php/berlinstudies/article/view/60>

2. M.S. Olimov. O'rta masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarda jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini shakllanish dinamikasi. Fan-sportga. Ilmiy nazariy jurnal. 2021 y. 2-son. 16-18b. e-mail: fan_sportga@uzdjtsu.uz

3. Muxsinbek Olimov. Yengil atletikachilarning ko'p yillik tayyorgarlik bosqichlarida mashg'ulot yuklamalarini taqsimlash va boshqarish texnologiyasi. Pedagogik mahorat. Ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal 3-son (2021-yil, iyun).

4. Olimov, Muxsinbek Sotiboldiyevich (2021) "A method of special physical training of short-distance runners in athletics", *Eurasian Journal of Sport Science*: Vol. 1: Iss. 2, Article 17. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/eajss/vol1/iss2/17>

5. Muhsin Olimov. O'rta masofaga yuguruvchilarning musobaqa oldi tayyorgarlik mashg'ulotlarini rejalashtirish. Pedagogik mahorat. Ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal. 1-son (2021-yil, fevral).

6. Iqrorjon Roziqovich Soliev, Larisa Vladimirovna Smurygina. TECHNOLOGIES FOR PREPARING RUNNERS AVERAGE DISTANCES TO COMPETITION. Emergent: JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL DISCOVERIES AND LIFELONG LEARNING (EJEDL). 2776-0995 Volume 2, Issue 10, Oct, 2021. 21-27.

<https://ejedl.academiascience.org/index.php/ejedl/article/view/144>

7. Soliev I.R., Khaydarov B., Mirzatillaev I., Khojamkeldiev G., Ziyaev F., Functional training level of runners student-athletes sprinters. G'G' International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, Vol. 24, Issue 05, 2020, <http://www.psychosocial.com/article/PR201878/17061>

8. Soliev I.R., Davidova K.R., Azamova G. E. Analysis of the training and management process management system in athletics. Academic Research in Educational Sciences. Volume2/Special issue 1/2021

9. Rakhimova.D Z G' Improving the physical training of triathlons in the training group G'G' Academic research in educational sciences. Volume 1/ Issue 3/2020

10. Soliev I.R., Kholbekova D.N., Davlatyorova L. B., Azamova G. E. G'G' Improvement of technical training in short running athletics. G'G' Academic Research in Educational Sciences. Volume2/Special issue 1/2021

11. O'ktamov Dilyorbek Tojiboyevich Development of Functional Fitness of Long-Distance Runners Vol. 1 (2022): Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences

12. O'ktamov Dilyorbek Tojiboevich Uzoq masofaga yuguruvchilarni funksional tayyorgarlik darajasini tuzilishi. 2181-1717 (E) Obrazovaniye i innovatsionno'ye issledovaniya (2022 god 6.2) 53-58str.

13. Oktamov Dilyorbek Tajiboyevich International scientific journal
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8.2

**STRUCTURE OF THE LEVEL OF PREPARATION OF LONG-DISTANCE
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